

Pediatric rotation in General Practice specialty training: Bridging the gap between Evaluation theory and Practice

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ABSTRACT Practitioners and Paediatricians occupy the fulcrum of healthcare service delivery for babies, children and young people in any climes. Evaluation of paediatric rotation in general practice speciality training can have a significant impact on the quality general practice trainee and ultimately health care system and service delivery. Stakeholders of both trainee groups can benefit from collaboration and synergy using the evaluation model to improve training delivery. This narrative review aims to critically appraise educational intervention in paediatrics rotation of general practice speciality training from the perspective of published theories, models and application of evaluation models. Different evaluation models are reported in association with various underpinning theories and an analysis of how educational programmes and possible collaboration between the two specialities can relate. This paper intends to guide the evaluation of paediatric training in general practice.

KEYWORDS Paediatric training, general practice training, medical education, health care evaluation, evaluation approaches

Introduction

General Practitioners and Paediatricians occupy the fulcrum of healthcare service delivery for babies, children and young people in any climes. There is a significant and palpable perception that some of the traditional boundaries that exists between these professionals must be dismantled to provide a sound and effective healthcare service delivery for children, young people and their family with the right doctor who has the necessary tested and proven expertise to deliver cutting edge care and training. The demand for the training of multi-disciplinary, multi-professional and interdisciplinary synergism in association with service delivery concept is essential to standard, result-oriented and impact making healthcare delivery system. The overall educational goal for the paediatric rotation of the Gen-

eral practice training is for the trainee to gain competence in managing the diverse paediatric condition in the community and recognition of conditions that need a referral. This paper aims to critically appraise educational intervention in paediatrics rotation of general practice speciality training from the perspective of published theories, models and application of evaluation. The full training programme for general practice currently lasts a minimum of three years from ST1 to ST 3. Training includes 18 months of hospital specialities rotation including obstetrics and gynaecology, paediatrics, geriatric medicine, accident and emergency or psychiatry. Additional 18 months spent in GP surgery in General Practice. Educational evaluation is the measurement of progress towards meeting educational objective [1], and this is to provide significant information and data on how effective educational program is and furthermore to make recommendations to maximise outcomes to improve patient care[2]. "The care provided by UK children's health services is inferior in many regards to that in comparable European countries. Although there are many examples of good practice, health services too often provide poor outcomes and are seemingly planned around the needs of organisations rather than those of children, young people, and families."[3]. General Practitioners and Paediatricians sit at the heart of health care for babies, children and young people. Currently, the need for

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fruitful collaboration is at its highest call hence conventional boundaries between these professionals must be broken down and build a bridge to provide a high-quality health service for the child and their family with the right doctor who has the necessary expertise. Poor health outcomes for children in the UK, the demand for service redesign, and the imperatives for change in training demand multi-professional and interdisciplinary collaboration [4]. “Despite the high number of children coming into their surgeries, many GPs have little or no experience of paediatrics as part of their professional training. This means that, technical competence notwithstanding, many GPs lack the confidence to assess and treat children effectively, something that comes from specialist training and experience.” [5]. General Practitioners currently have a three-year model of training. RCPCH data [6] posits that only 50-60% of GPs, in many parts of the country, have had any formal paediatric & child health training outside their general practice posts. The training and exposure that trainees get during general practice training posts can be remarkable if their GP trainer is highly confident in managing children, but equally, it can be less so if the trainer had no dedicated paediatric training or limited interest in paediatrics or child health. A training model called Learning Together has been shown to make a difference with regards to learning outcomes for both specialities including clinical knowledge and skills, and professional outcomes of ongoing collaboration and attitudes. In an early audit of four common conditions across 22 GP practices and 9 trusts in London where Learning Together clinics took place, good practice moved from 57% before the clinics to 72% during (p-value < 0.01) and increased to 76% after the clinics, (p-value < 0.01 compared to before). Learning together clinics can be a positive lever for change [7]. Due to inadequate exposure of general practice trainees to general and community paediatrics, there is changing demography, the possibility of same changes occurring in the community-based training environment of general practice registrars is unknown. Currently, as a core requirement of Australian vocational training, general practice registrars are required to complete a paediatric hospital rotation or an emergency department rotation with a significant paediatric caseload. Furthermore, Australian GP trainee is expected to encounter numerous paediatric patients in the community-based setting during their clinical placements in primary care practices [8].

Formative Evaluation of Paediatric Rotation in General Practice Specialty Training The e-portfolio is used in paediatric rotation of the general practice specialty train to collect and collate evidence of learning, performance and progress in a systematic fashion. It can also be described as a formative assessment tool for gathering of assessment and record of attainment in line with curriculum of competence expected to be attained under the keen supervision of clinical supervisor (Consultant Paediatrician) and General practitioner (educational supervisor). It is designed to facilitate feedbacks and reflections. It's not an examination tool but very significant part of final summative assessment to qualify as GP. For paediatric rotation, it consists of a minimum of three case-based discussion (CBD), three mini clinical examinations (MiniCEX) and directly observed procedure (DOPS) with other log entries of reflections. There is no organised or systematic supervision by the clinical supervision, the majority of trainee used their initiative, but most times educational supervisors can play an advisory role.

Theories Supporting Educational Program Evaluation Models Program evaluation is an essential part of medical education, relevant theories are important in understanding evaluation

models which most times focus on the change. Reductionism Theory of reductionism asserts that a program or an outcome can be totally understood and thus predicted by investigating and understanding its constituent parts [9]. This cause-effect dimension needs an assumption of linearity, advocating that once the contributing factors of an outcome are known by program success or failure in achieving those outcomes can be explained [10]. One of the constituent's parts of GP training scheme is Paediatrics and child health, but most current trainees had no paediatric posting their training rotation hence the outcome can be predicted, their confidence will be impaired when dealing with paediatric cases in general practice.

System Theory

This theory asserts that that program outcome is not just explained just by its constituent part but by relationship between and among those parts and their environment. Furthermore, this theory showed that change is an inherent part of the system and their relationship with other parts will produce dynamic and active change [10]. The relationship between general practice and paediatrics is so intertwined that they co-exist in huge dimension and this relationship produce significant changes positively or negatively depending on the investment of paediatric exposure on GP training speciality.

Complexity Theory

This is a constellation of diverse theories, have been used commonly in medical education. The used of this theory provides practitioners with an in-depth understanding of interconnectivity, synergy and networking in evaluation [11], illustrated in figure 1, General practice and paediatric training and health care delivery are hugely interconnected despite occasional complexity this can be managed with an appropriate action plan, protocol and guideline some already in place.

Fig. 1 Complexity Theory (Source: Cohen et al., 2007).

Table 1 Evaluation Models

MODEL	THEORY	CONSIDERATIONS	ADVANTAGES	VALUE
CIPP model	Social system theory and complexity theory.	Does not assume lineate causality. Accounts for the complexity of medical, educational programmes. More complex data analysis.	Focus on programme improvement. Pays attention to multiple sources of inputs.	It is used in the process of evaluating, planning, implementation (formative), and outcomes (summative, retrospective). Provides valuable information on why outcomes were observed. Best to inform on the cost-effectiveness of selected approaches.
Experimental and Quasi-Experimental Models	Reductionist theory.	Ethical considerations. Expensive (experimental). Assumes linear causality. Does not account for complex environment interactions in results.	Familiar design in a medical environment.	Provides evidence on reasons outcomes were observed or not. Appropriate when high internal validity is more important. Useful when comparing pre- and post-intervention results.
Kirkpatrick's model	Reductionist theory.	Assumes linear causality. Does not account for variables that affect learning.	A clear focus on outcomes.	Can be used with other models to define specifically the outcomes of the programme.

Experimental/quasi-experimental models

The purpose of an experimental model is to outline any outcome brought about by an intervention. Two groups are evaluated, one in which the change has been implemented and a control group for comparative reasons. Experiments and quasi-experiments are methods of research which stem from a natural experiment approach, focusing on naturally occurring circumstances and targeting specific interventions [12]. Quasi-experiments differ from experimental models in that randomisation is eliminated in Quasi-experiments [13]. Quasi-experimental models of evaluation test a descriptive causal hypothesis about manipulatable causes [14] with non-randomised assigned control groups. Experimental designs equally make observations about intervention but are randomly allocated. They provide the most information about possible cause-and-effect relationships [15]. Suchman in 1967 [16] has led the development of principles for evaluation research differentiating between evaluation considered as a judgement and evaluation research based on scientific grounds. Contemporary approaches are based on

Shadish's work [14] which deals with the generalisation of causal connections [14], [17]. This model is essential in evaluating the effectiveness of pre and post intervention of educational and training programs in General Practice as it relates to Paediatric training, how far has this positive impact of the new set of General practitioners in dealing with paediatric cases confidently in communities.

Kirkpatrick model

Kirkpatrick's model of evaluation is a common model for evaluating learner's outcomes in training programs (Kirkpatrick's) like general practice and paediatric training speciality. It consists of four levels of the hierarchy of program outcome as illustrated in figure 2; the first level deals with learner's satisfaction by evaluating their reaction to the program, the second level assesses the impact of training on learner's behaviour in terms of knowledge, skills and attitude, the e-portfolio can provide some insight into this. The third level how much information learners can apply to their workplace and practice. Finally, the

fourth level assesses the impact of this new learning at the patient or community level [10]. However, the drawback here is that this evaluation model does not consider the interaction between different elements of the program hence the interaction between Paediatrics and general practice should be mutual, synergistic, communal and interdependent in training, practice and healthcare delivery in the community for huge impact and undeniable positive outcomes.

THE KIRKPATRICK MODEL

Fig. 2 The Kirkpatrick Model (Adapted from Petrone, 2017).

Context/Input/Process/Product model (CIPP Model)

This model was first described by Daniel Stufflebeam in 1971[19] made up of four set of evaluation component including context (baseline for evaluating later outcomes), Input (Cost-effectiveness of alternative or competing approaches to educational need), Process (assess implementation of a program) and product (assesses program outcome, positive or negative). Furthermore, CIPP embraces complexity theory, the diversity of programmes and the non-linear relationships and changes occurring therein, deeming it useful in evaluation [10]. This model systematically investigates the value of a programme by obtaining ongoing data and reports on critical information at each step of programme implementation. It informs stakeholders on the quality, worth, feasibility, cost-effectiveness, impact and safety of the programme outcomes, therefore aligning to Programme Evaluation Standards in terms of utility, feasibility, accuracy and accountability [22]. Training, teaching and practice in Paediatrics and General practice are hugely capital intensive; hence any cut back from the specialities will negatively impact on training and healthcare delivery in the long run. Meticulous assessment between stakeholders in Government, training and teaching is inevitable before any financial and non-financial adjustment.

Discussion

Underpinning theories form the basis for evaluation models (Table 1). Reductionism understands systems by breaking it down into smaller components and assessing the impact of these components. In contrast, system theory, states that to understand a system, components should not be investigated individually, but at the relationships and interactions between components, within the system's environment. Also, complexity

Fig. 3 Key Components of the CIPP Evaluation Model and Associated Relationships with Programmes (Source: Stufflebeam & Shinkfield, 2007)

theory assesses several areas in a system, to understand its interconnectedness and networking. Based on the Kirkpatrick model, paediatric rotation learning in general practice training can be monitored with the use of e-portfolio and formative assessment of it can be done which will ultimately translate to summative assessment in the award of MRCPG diploma. CIPP model (Figure 3) is a proven way to assess the outcome of training and learning as per paediatric rotation in a GP practice. Trainees at three of Ireland's 14 specialist GP training schemes were surveyed 82 different clinical skills and presentations common in practice of Paediatrics in General Practice setting with forty-five percent (58/128) response scored on Likert scale, hospital-based trainees rate their competence in Paediatrics as 3.67/5 and practice-based trainees scoring their competence as 4.13/5, furthermore trainees were asked to comment on their confidence performing selected paediatric skills and treatment of some common paediatric cases, low level of confidence was reported in assessment of mental and physical development skills, vision and hearing assessment, management of food intolerance, sleep problems, non-accidental injury among many others [20]. These findings are consistent with findings of GP training programs internationally, training in Paediatrics for GPs varies between European countries but is generally considered to be too short [21]. General practice trainees may need more opportunities for exposure to paediatrics especially in those areas with perceived low confidence in skills and practice; this could be done even in General Practice under supervision of experienced General practitioners with a paediatric interest in association with community paediatricians.

Conclusion

An evaluation of the complex and ever-changing world of medical, educational programmes like paediatric rotation in GP training is explored. Different evaluation models are reported in association with various underpinning theories and an analysis of how educational programmes and possible collaboration

between the two specialities can relate. This paper intends to guide the evaluation of paediatric training in general practice.

Competing Interests

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